

THE INFLUENCE OF AMINO-ACIDS ON THE AUTOXIDATION OF ASCORBIC ACID

BY P. C. RAKSHIT, B. C. SEN AND P. K. BHATTACHARYYA

The autoxidation of ascorbic acid in solution has been studied in presence of different amino-acids, like glycine, alanine, glutamic acid, aspartic acid, leucine etc., and amides like asparagine and guanidine. When these compounds are present in molecular proportions to ascorbic acid or in higher proportions, they exhibit a strong stabilising influence on the autoxidation. The amino-acids suffer no chemical change. The stabilising effect decreases with increase of temperature and p_H . It is suggested that this effect is probably due to a kind of loose association with ascorbic acid.

The most remarkable property of ascorbic acid is its reducing action which renders it liable to easy oxidation. This is obviously due to the two hydroxyl groups attached to the double bond in the closed lactone ring. In consequence, the substance avidly takes up oxygen in neutral and even in slightly acidic medium, to suffer the reversible conversion to dehydroascorbic acid.

Some of the early workers (Kellie and Zilva, *Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 1028; Baron *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, 112, 625), mostly using natural ascorbic acid, suggested that pure ascorbic acid did not undergo autoxidation. The spontaneous aerobic change is due to the presence of traces of positive catalysts, specially copper ions. Ghosh *et al.* (*Biochem. Z.*, 1936, 289, 15; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1937, 118, 246) showed that solutions of synthetic ascorbic acid suffered reversible autoxidation between p_H 6.8 and 7.2, with no trace of iron or copper.

This autoxidation acquires a special importance when the influence of other substances, specially those with which it is associated in nature, is studied. To illustrate, Caro and Gianni (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1934, 223, 13) observed that sugars had no influence on its autoxidation. Traces of sulphhydryl compounds completely suspended the oxygen uptake by ascorbic acid solution at about p_H 7.0 (Ghosh *et al.*, *Biochem. Z.*, 1936, 289, 15; 1937, 291, 330). Chlorophyll also exerts inhibitory action on the process (Giroud, *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1934, 117, 612; Rakshit, *Biochem. Z.*, 1938, 297, 153; Bessey, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, 103, 687).

Occasional observations are also recorded on the effect of amino-acids on the autoxidation of ascorbic acid. In growing tissues of plants, protein-ascorbic acid complex is supposed to exist and be decomposed at higher temperature (Reidman *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1938, 32, 85). Caro *et al.* reported that glycine and alanine exhibited some retarding influence on the autoxidation of ascorbic acid (*Chem. Abs.*, 1944, 6383; 1943, 6719; *J. Osaka Med. Soc.*, 1940, 39, 473). But Peterson and Walton (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1212) found glutamic acid, aspartic acid and cysteine not to retard aerobic decomposition of ascorbic acid. Krishnamurthi and Giri (this *Journal*, 1941, 18, 191) found that amongst others, glycine and alanine partially prevented autoxidation of

ascorbic acid, when catalysed by copper. It is reported that valine, leucine, histidine, arginine etc. cannot protect the oxidation of ascorbic acid (*Kyoto Univ. Bull. Res. Inst. Food. Sci.*, 1949, 1, 35). It was therefore considered necessary to make a detailed study of the influence of amino-acids on the aerobic oxidation of ascorbic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthetic ascorbic acid of Hofman-la-Roche was used throughout. Its purity was checked up by titration against I_2 (solution) and optical rotation. Amino-acids and other chemicals used were of reagent quality. All solutions were made from bidistilled water from all-pyrex stills. Special precautions were taken to avoid contamination of the catalysts. The absence of copper and iron ions was always confirmed by rubenic acid, sulphocyanides etc.

The oxidation was studied by bubbling pure air at a considerably rapid rate (approx. 70-80 bubbles per min.) through a definite volume of the solution. In each of these experiments, a blank control was also linked to the system without the amino-acid, so that any variation in the external factors could be counteracted. The p_H was rigorously kept constant in each of the reaction and control vessels. Normally phosphate buffers were used; acetate and borate buffers were employed only in special cases.

The apparatus for studying the oxidation was a simple one. Two wide-mouthed pyrex tubes fitted with rubber corks, carrying delivery tubes, were used as oxidation vessels and the control. Equal volumes of the solution of the reaction mixture and its blank were taken in them and subjected to the same continuous flow of washed and purified air through them in fine bubbles. The temperature of the reaction vessels was kept constant correct to $\pm 1^\circ$.

From time to time an aliquot part of the reaction mixture as also the blank was pipetted off into dilute H_2SO_4 and quickly titrated against the standard iodine solution ($\approx N/100$).

The first set of experiments were to establish that the solution of ascorbic acid, even when free from detectable traces of Cu and Fe ions, suffered oxidation in air at p_H 7.0 and at different temperatures. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

$p_H = 6.8$

Conc. of ascorbic acid.	Temp.	I_2 conc. (N/100)	Iodine titre for 1 c.c. soln. after 180 min.	% Ascorbic acid oxidised.
0.02 $\approx M$	35°	1.0024	1.85 c.c.	61.0
0.0238	25°	1.082	1.95	56.7
0.0229	0°	1.010	3.40	25.3

The oxidation was then studied in presence of several amino compounds: glycine, alanine, glutamic acid, aspartic acid, leucine, guanidine and asparagine. The influ-

ence of each of them was also studied with variation of p_H , temperature, etc. As a general rule, these substances protect ascorbic acid against aerobic oxidation. The results are shown in Tables II and III.

TABLE II

Conc. of ascorbic acid.	Reaction mixture Asc. acid : amino-acid.	p_H .	Temp.	I ₂ titre of ascorbic acid at		% Ascorbic acid oxidised.	
				0 min.	180 min.	Blank.	Reaction vessel.
Glycine.							
0.0998	2:1	6.9	24°	6.35	4.95	28.0	22.0
0.105	1:1	6.9	"	6.35	5.75	30.4	9.5
0.101	1:4	6.9	"	6.25	6.06	28.0	4.0
0.0515	1:2	6.7	"	4.75	4.30	23.7	9.5
0.05	1:2	7.1	"	4.50	4.00	41.0	11.0
0.0501	1:2	7.8	25°	4.50	3.10	51.7	31.0
0.103	1:2	6.8	30°	6.40	5.20	37.0	18.7
Alanine.							
0.053	1:1	6.9	25°	8.50	5.80	49.4	31.8
"	1:2	"	"	3.25	2.30	55.4	29.0
"	1:2.5	"	"	8.70	6.60	57.8	24.0
"	1:4	6.8	"	8.80	6.95	43.5	21.0

Estimation of the Amino-acids:—After definite intervals of time, not only the ascorbic acid was estimated, but also the amino-acids, in order to ascertain if the latter would participate the chemical process. Glycine and alanine were estimated by alkali titration by fixing the NH_2 group with formaldehyde. Glutamic acid was estimated by Pope and Stevens' method (*Biochem. J.*, 1939, 33, 1069) by forming copper-complex. Asparagine was estimated colorimetrically by matching the intense blue colour of its copper-complex with standards prepared with known quantities. The amounts of guanidine were determined gravimetrically (Sharp, *ibid.*, 1920, 14, 46) as picrates.

Influence of Glycine and Alanine on the Autoxidation of Ascorbic Acid.—In Table III are incorporated the results of the influence of glycine and alanine on the oxidation of ascorbic acid by air under different conditions of temperature, p_H etc.

Obviously, the two amino-acids stabilise the vitamin against aerobic oxidation. In most of these experiments the amino-acid was estimated, and not the slightest change in its concentration was observed. The stabilising effect increased with increased amino-acid concentration.

The Influence of other Amino Compounds.—Leucine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid as well as guanidine and asparagine also exert inhibitory action on the autoxidation of the ascorbic acid. The summarised results are only recorded in Table III.

It is evident from the results shown above, that not only the amino-acids but also some amides like guanidine and asparagine protect ascorbic acid from autoxidation, and the rate of oxidation is found to decrease with increasing concentration of ascorbic

acid. When the amino-acids are present in quantities less than one-fourth of that of ascorbic acid in molar proportions, there is no stabilising effect. The amides tried here have a greater effect.

TABLE III

Reaction mix. Asc. acid : glutamic acid.	pH .	Temp.	% Ascorbic acid oxidised in 180 mins.	
			Blank vessel.	Reaction vessel.
1:1	6.8	25°	56.7	11.4
1:2	"	"	56.7	13.7
1:1	"	"	56.7	37.5
2:1	"	"	59.0	44.3
1:2	7.8	"	42.8	12.9
1:2	6.2	"	61.8	26.6
1:2	6.8	0°	25.3	4.5
1:2	"	35°	61.1	15.0
Asc. acid : aspartic acid.				
1:4	"	25°	64.9	15.2
1:2	"	"	64.4	16.6
1:7	"	"	64.2	23.1
2:1	"	"	62.0	31.1
1:2	"	0°	30.1	8.3
1:2	"	35°	71.0	30.6
Asc. acid : leucine.				
1:2	"	25°	66.0	4.2
2:3	"	"	71.4	9.6
2:1	"	"	71.4	11.7
Asc. acid : isoleucine.				
1:2	7.6	25°	61	8.2
1:2	6.8	35°	75.4	9.2
Asc. acid : asparagine.				
1:2	6.8	25°	69	13.4
3:2	"	"	69	16.6
5:1	"	"	63	42.7
10:1	"	"	63	54.7
1:2	7.8	"	61	23.6
Asc. acid : guanidine				
1:2	6.8	25°	69	6.3
1:1	"	"	66.3	17.9
1:2 (approx)	6.0	30°	54	8.0

The idea that amino-acids remove the positive catalysts (such as copper) and thereby exercise a protecting action may be rejected on the ground that this effect is observed only when the proportion of amino-acid to ascorbic acid is equal, or even greater. The possibility of amino acid inhibiting the reaction by using up some of the oxygen is also discarded by the fact that the contents of amino compounds remain unchanged after the reaction. We can only suggest that since molecular proportions of amino acids seem to be essential for inhibition of the autoxidation, there may be the formation of a loose molecular compound between the ascorbic acid and the amino-acid, rendering

the vulnerable OH groups inactive in the oxidation process. It must be remembered that amino-acid can prevent aerobic oxidation but not the iodometric oxidation of the ascorbic acid molecule.

The presence of ammonium salts, sugars, acetamide, urea and other simple amines has no effect on the spontaneous aerobic oxidation of ascorbic acid. β -Amino-acids, or aminobenzoic acids cannot also inhibit the process. It is therefore likely that there is a loose association, which prevents the formation of the intermediate tetrahydroxy compounds known to be first formed during autoxidation.

PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received August 3, 1956.